

Evaluating the Feasibility of POD–AE Hybrid Frameworks for Parametric Reactor Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Recent advancements in data-driven modeling have generated strong interest in applying such techniques to reactor physics problems, aiming to accelerate high-fidelity simulations while retaining spatial accuracy. Among these methods, Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) has emerged as a reliable linear Reduced Order Model (ROM) capable of reconstructing reactor quantities of interest with significantly reduced computational cost. However, its linear nature limits its ability to represent nonlinear dependencies in the solution space, especially under strong perturbations. To address this limitation, this work explores nonlinear and hybrid extensions of POD through the integration of Autoencoders (AEs).

Four reconstruction strategies are investigated: pure POD, pure AE, hybrid POD–AE, and learnable-weighted POD–AE. The hybrid model equally combines linear and nonlinear latent representations, while the learnable-weighted version introduces trainable parameters to adaptively balance the POD and AE contributions. The models are evaluated using the eVinciTM Motivated Design (EMD) microreactor, focusing on reconstructing three-dimensional pin power distributions for 37 representative control drum configurations derived from Serpent simulations.

Results show that while the linear POD provides a solid baseline with mean RMS and maximum absolute errors of 0.84% and 5.63%, respectively, the learnable-weighted POD–AE achieves the best performance with errors of 0.72% and 6.02%. Although the improvement is modest, the findings demonstrate that nonlinear learning can enhance the expressiveness of projection-based models. The limitations of the approach presented here most likely stem from insufficient training data for the AEs. Future efforts will incorporate regression within the nonlinear latent space and residual learning to further reduce reconstruction error and improve predictive capability.

Keywords: Reduced Order Modeling, Proper Orthogonal Decomposition, Autoencoder, Hybrid Models, Microreactor Pin Power Reconstruction

1. INTRODUCTION

Data-driven modeling has recently gained traction in reactor analysis [1, 2] and radiation transport research [3], aiming to develop Reduced-Order Models (ROMs) that reproduce high-fidelity spatial behaviors while greatly reducing computational cost. Instead of directly solving transport equations, such models use algebraic reconstruction or neural network–based frameworks for rapid and accurate evaluations across operating conditions. Among these methods, the Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) approach remains one of the most reliable and interpretable in reactor physics. By applying a truncated Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) to Full-Order Model (FOM) datasets, POD extracts orthogonal basis modes representing the dominant energy content of the system. The solution can then be reconstructed as a linear combination of these modes using a compact set of POD coefficients. Prior studies [1, 2, 3] confirmed its efficiency but also highlighted the high cost of generating training data. To address this, our previous work [4] introduced a Sequential Optimal Experimental Design

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(sOED)-based framework that optimally selects informative samples, reducing simulation effort while preserving predictive accuracy.

Despite its success, POD and other linear subspace methods face a fundamental limitation known as the Kolmogorov n -width barrier [5]. In many reactor and transport problems, the solution manifold exhibits slow spectral decay, requiring large linear bases for accurate representation. This becomes critical in strongly nonlinear systems, such as those with large control-drum rotations or complex flux redistributions, where linear ROMs fail to capture higher-order correlations. Nonlinear dimensionality-reduction techniques, particularly Autoencoders (AEs), address this challenge by learning compact nonlinear manifolds that encode and reconstruct the original field. Hybrid POD–AE models combine the stability and interpretability of linear methods with the expressive power of neural networks, offering improved accuracy for complex reactor problems.

The present work investigates hybrid and learnable-weighted POD–AE frameworks for reconstructing three-dimensional pin power distributions in a microreactor. Building upon the dataset and methodology of [4], this study evaluates whether learning a nonlinear representation can reduce reconstruction errors compared to purely linear approaches. Four configurations are considered: (i) pure POD, (ii) pure AE, (iii) hybrid POD–AE, and (iv) learnable-weighted POD–AE. The latter concept was first proposed in [6], while the hybrid POD–AE idea originates from [7]. Using the eVinciTM Motivated Design (EMD) microreactor [8] as a benchmark, each model is assessed by its ability to reproduce detailed pin power distributions across varying control-drum positions. This investigation focuses on evaluating the feasibility of nonlinear learning to enhance POD reconstruction accuracy and establish a foundation for future regression-driven nonlinear ROMs.

2. BACKGROUND

In this section, we present a concise yet essential background to aid the reader’s understanding of the work that follows. At first we want to develop some mathematical notation that will describe our problems.

- θ the vector (or scalar) representing high-fidelity model input parameters
- $L(\theta)$ the FOM or high-fidelity simulation executed with inputs θ
- \mathbf{x} output of the FOM. Nominally this is some engineering Quantity of Interest (QoI) that is a finite length discrete vector (in this work it is the 3D pin power distribution). So, for a specific input θ_k

$$\mathbf{x}_k = L(\theta_k) . \quad (1)$$

- $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ output of the ROM, or estimated FOM output. So,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k = \tilde{L}(\theta_k) . \quad (2)$$

- $\tilde{L}(\theta)$ our ROM (evaluated with inputs θ)
- $\mathcal{D}_x^{(K)}$ the set of high-fidelity simulation data consisting of K input-output pairs

$$\mathcal{D}_x^{(K)} = \{\theta_i, \mathbf{x}_i\}_{i=1}^K . \quad (3)$$

For the reduced order model based on a reduced basis approach we define the abstract projection operator \mathcal{P} as the reconstruction of the high-dimensional output from the latent space.

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{z}_k) , \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{z}_k represents the low-dimensional latent space (i.e. consistent with Equation (1)); \mathbf{x}_k is the high-dimensional data for some engineering application; \mathcal{P} is the projection operator. To map from the high-dimensional data to low-dimensional data, we write

$$\mathbf{z}_k = \mathcal{P}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}_k) , \quad (5)$$

where \mathcal{P}^\dagger is like a compression operator taking high-dimensional data and compressing it to a low-dimensional latent space. Typically, \mathcal{P}^\dagger is related to \mathcal{P} and can be thought of like an inverse operator to \mathcal{P} , but it is not necessarily always consistent with the concept of a matrix inverse.

We are defining the reconstruction error as the difference between our ROM and FOM

$$\varepsilon(\theta) = \left\| \mathbf{x}(\theta) - \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{P}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}(\theta))) \right\|_p, \quad (6)$$

In this work, we are considering 2-norm and ∞ -norm.

2.1. Proper Orthogonal Decomposition

To implement a basic POD [9, 10] model used for the ROMs, we can perform an SVD on our data matrix as follows:

$$\mathbf{x}(\theta) = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^T \approx \mathbf{\Psi}_r\mathbf{\Sigma}_r\mathbf{V}_r^T. \quad (7)$$

In Equation (7), θ is our parametric input—specifically control drum angle; $\mathbf{\Psi}_r$ is the POD basis (or POD modes) which is chosen to be as the first r column vectors of the left singular vectors, \mathbf{U} .

To be consistent with the previous notation in Equations (4), (5) and (7) we are defining the “Projection Operator” and “Inverse Projection Operator” for POD as follows:

$$\mathbf{z}_{POD} = \mathcal{P}_{POD}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{\Sigma}_r\mathbf{V}_r^T = \mathbf{\Psi}_r^T\mathbf{x}. \quad (8)$$

Accordingly,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{POD} = \mathcal{P}_{POD}(\mathbf{z}_{POD}) = \mathbf{\Psi}_r(\mathbf{\Psi}_r^T\mathbf{x}). \quad (9)$$

2.2. Autoencoder

Autoencoders (AEs) are unsupervised Neural Networks (NNs) designed to learn efficient representations of input data by compressing the data into a latent space and reconstructing the original input from this compressed form [11]. This encoding-decoding architecture incentivizes the model to extract the most salient features from the data (when possible), by forcing the information through the “bottleneck” structure of the AE. Therefore, AEs are considered appropriate tools for dimensionality reduction. Moreover, the ability to capture nonlinear structures allows AEs to be particularly effective for modeling certain complex physical systems [12].

The general structure of an AE is depicted in Figure 1. It consists of two neural networks, the encoder and decoder. AEs are basically trained like any other Artificial Neural Network (ANN) where weights and biases for the neurons are determined through repeated optimization with gradient descent. This process is well documented in several references, and we refer the reader to [6] for more information.

Unlike typical feed-forward NNs, we do not need a separate output for each input-output pair in the training because the output of the AE should be equivalent to the input. Because the training process of the AE is similar to other ANNs, they have similar hyper-parameters to consider to produce the most accurate model. The hyper-parameters typically considered for an AE are: activation function, dimensionality of the latent space, number of hidden layers in the encoder/decoder, number of neurons in each hidden layer of the encoder/decoder, learning rate, loss function, and optimizer.

Finally, to be consistent with notation, we are defining “Projection Operator” and “Inverse Projection Operator” for AE as follows:

$$\mathbf{z}_{AE} = \mathcal{P}_{AE}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}) = \mathcal{A}_E(\mathbf{x}), \quad (10)$$

and,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{AE} = \mathcal{P}_{AE}(\mathbf{z}_{AE}) = \mathcal{A}_D(\mathbf{z}_{AE}). \quad (11)$$

Figure 1. Illustration of Auto-Encoder Structure

2.3. Simple Hybrid POD-AE based ROM

The simple hybrid POD–AE ROM combines the latent representations and reconstructions obtained from the traditional POD and the AE with equal weighting. As shown in Equation (12), the latent variable \mathbf{z}_{hyb} is computed as the arithmetic mean of the POD and AE latent spaces. The reconstructed field, given in Equation (13), is similarly formed by averaging the POD-projected and AE-decoded outputs. This simple hybridization provides a balanced contribution from both linear (POD) and nonlinear (AE) representations, with expectation of improving the overall reconstruction quality while maintaining interpretability.

$$\mathbf{z}_{hyb} = 0.5 \times \mathbf{z}_{POD} + 0.5 \times \mathbf{z}_{AE} \quad (12)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{hyb} = 0.5 \times \mathcal{P}_{POD}(\mathbf{z}_{POD}) + 0.5 \times \mathcal{A}_D(\mathbf{z}_{hyb}) \quad (13)$$

In using a fixed weight here, we show the importance of determining a correct weight along with the NN parameters with our next hybrid model.

2.4. Learnable Weighted POD-AE based ROM

In this formulation, the contribution of the POD and AE components to the output is learned adaptively through trainable weights. As shown in Equation (14), a learnable gate α controls the relative importance of the latent representations from the POD and AE, applied through component-wise multiplication. Similarly, Equation (15) introduces a learnable matrix \mathbf{B} that modulates the blending of the two reconstructions in the output space. This learnable weighting scheme enables the model to dynamically emphasize the component, linear or nonlinear, that best captures the underlying structure of the data. This provides improved flexibility and accuracy over the fixed-weight hybrid approach.

$$\mathbf{z}_{hyb} = (\mathbf{1} - \alpha) \circ \mathbf{z}_{POD} + \alpha \circ \mathbf{z}_{AE} \quad (14)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{hyb} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}) \times \mathcal{P}_{POD}(\mathbf{z}_{POD}) + \mathbf{B} \times \mathcal{A}_D(\mathbf{z}_{hyb}) \quad (15)$$

Just to recall, our input (hence, output) matrix is of dimension $m \times n$, and the dimension of our latent space is $z \in \mathbb{R}^r$. In Equation (15), \mathbf{I} is an identity matrix of $\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $\mathbf{B} = \text{diag}(\beta)$. Also, α and β are learnable weights such that $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^r$ and $\beta \in \mathbb{R}^n$.

2.5. Few details about the models

In this model, the AE architecture is designed to be symmetric. After hyperparameter tuning, the number of hidden layers was set to four, with 2048, 512, 128, and 32 neurons, respectively. The latent dimension was also hyper-tuned and determined to be 8. Accordingly, the POD basis was truncated to $r = 8$ to ensure consistency between the two representations. A random 80/10/10 split was used for training, testing, and validation to ensure balanced model evaluation and generalization. The learning rate was set to 1×10^{-3} , and the batch size was kept at one due to the limited number of training samples. Training was carried out for 150 epochs.

For consistency, the same autoencoder structure was applied to the other two models as well. In the learnable-weighted model, the vectors α and β were initialized as zero vectors, so the model initially behaved as a pure POD formulation and progressively trained to learn the information from the AE's latent space during training.

It is also worth noting that the latent representations \mathbf{z}_{POD} and \mathbf{z}_{AE} possess opposite structures. Therefore, \mathbf{z}_{POD} is transposed before blending. Moreover, since these two latent spaces exist on different numerical scales, both were normalized prior to the blending process.

3. BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF EVINCI™ MOTIVATED DESIGN (EMD) REACTOR MODEL

The reactor analyzed in this work is a graphite moderated, sodium heat pipe microreactor concept inspired by the Westinghouse eVinci™ design. This configuration, described in [8], is referred to as the eVinci™ Motivated Design (EMD) reactor. It employs 20% enriched TRISO fuel, graphite as moderator, a BeO reflector, and sodium heat pipes for heat transport. The core measures 130 cm by 280 cm and delivers 4 MW_{th} nominal power with 1182 fuel pins, 656 heat pipes, and 12 control drums, as shown in Figure 2.

Simulations are performed under hot full power, beginning-of-life conditions using the Serpent Monte Carlo code [13]. Each pin is axially divided into 50 regions, with 20,000 particles per generation, 50 inactive cycles, and 5,000 active cycles. A full-core symmetric model is used, applying vacuum boundary conditions. All drums are positioned identically, and the drum angle is defined as the degree of withdrawal from the fully inserted state.

Figure 2. 1/4 Symmetry radial and axial diagram of EMD with labeled core components

For the present analysis, Serpent was used to generate pin power distributions corresponding to control drum positions from 0° to 180° in 1° intervals. This produced a total of 181 distributions, denoted as $\mathcal{D}^{\text{full}}$. A separate study is currently examining the complete dataset $\mathcal{D}^{\text{full}}$ using regression-based approaches to evaluate potential performance gains. In this work, however, we use a subset consisting

of 37 evenly spaced drum positions at 5° intervals, consistent with the configuration described in [4]. For consistency across this and future related studies, this reduced dataset is referred to as \mathcal{D}^{37} .

4. RESULTS

The standard POD reconstruction (Figure 3a) provides a physically interpretable yet linearly constrained approximation of the pin power field. With a mean RMS error of about 0.84% and a maximum absolute error of 5.6%, the model effectively captures the dominant spatial modes but struggles to represent localized nonlinear variations caused by strong control-drum perturbations. This shortcoming becomes more pronounced as the drum angle increases, since the linear POD basis cannot fully describe the nonlinear response surface of the reactor physics solution.

(a) POD reconstruction error.

(b) AE-only model reconstruction error.

Figure 3. Pure models: POD vs AE reconstruction error.

In contrast, the AE-only model (Figure 3b) exhibits a mean RMS error of 1.11% and a maximum absolute deviation of 8.0%. While the AE can learn complex nonlinear mappings, the absence of physics-based structure makes it prone to overfitting localized features, which reduces its global accuracy. This behavior highlights a common limitation of purely data-driven models: they can be expressive but lack the physical regularization that helps maintain stability and interpretability.

The simple hybrid POD–AE model (Figure 4a) combines the strengths of both methods by averaging their latent representations and reconstructed outputs. This balanced fusion achieves a mean RMS error of 0.93% and a maximum absolute error of 6.25%, showing clear improvement over the AE-only case. However, the fixed equal weighting restricts its flexibility, i.e., regions dominated by nonlinear behavior still cannot be fully captured because the model cannot dynamically adjust how much each component contributes.

Finally, the learnable weighted POD–AE model (Figure 4b) introduces trainable parameters α and β to adaptively tune the contributions of the POD and AE both in latent and reconstruction spaces. This adaptive approach achieves the lowest mean RMS error (0.72%) and maximum absolute error (6.02%), demonstrating that the model can intelligently balance linear and nonlinear information depending on local solution complexity. In practice, this learnable blending allows the ROM to reproduce fine-scale spatial variations more accurately while preserving numerical stability and physical interpretability. Near-zero errors occur at a few low-complexity drum positions; since α and β vary smoothly, this behavior does not indicate overfitting. With limited training data, such localized dips are expected, and further work is underway with an expanded dataset.

A summary of the reconstruction performance for all ROM configurations is presented in Table I.

Table I. Comparison of reconstruction errors for different ROM configurations.

Model	Mean RMS Error (%)	Max Absolute Error (%)
Pure POD	0.84	5.63
Pure AE	1.11	8.04
Hybrid POD-AE	0.93	6.25
Learnable POD-AE	0.72	6.02

(a) Hybrid POD-AE reconstruction error.

(b) Learnable weighted POD-AE reconstruction error.

Figure 4. Hybrid models: fixed-weight vs learnable-weight POD-AE reconstruction error.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Recalling our primary objective, to reduce the reliance on expensive high-fidelity simulations, this work does not yet achieve that ultimate goal. Instead, it demonstrates the feasibility of reducing linear reconstruction errors through nonlinear methods. The main limitation remains the scarcity of training data for neural network models, which is inherently difficult to overcome for this type of problem since generating additional high-fidelity data is extremely costly. Despite this constraint, the results from the learnable hybrid approach show promising behavior. Although the improvement over the standard POD is modest, the findings suggest that nonlinear methods can effectively capture complex relationships in the data. It should also be noted that, we have a very few training data as compared to our features, which is affecting our results here. As noted by [14], autoencoders require a sufficiently large number of training samples to effectively learn meaningful feature representations and to prevent overfitting when data availability is limited.

As noted earlier, no regression model was used in this study; regression-based extensions of the POD models are being developed separately. The next step in advancing the nonlinear approach will involve performing regression in the nonlinear latent space. Additionally, ongoing work is exploring the use of different learning strategies to model residuals from the POD reconstruction.

Overall, substantial effort is still required to meet the broader objective of achieving a noticeable reduction in reconstruction error compared to purely linear approaches. Nevertheless, this study establishes a strong foundation for that continued research.

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